

**"DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION ISSUES OF DISTANCE
LEARNING IN MEDICAL EDUCATION SYSTEMS: EXAMPLES FROM
FOREIGN COUNTRIES"**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7978575>

Komilova M.O

Senior Lecturer at Tashkent Medical Academy,

Kasimova Oksana

Master's Degree student at Tashkent Medical Academy.

Abstract.

This review article examines the development and implementation issues of distance learning in medical education systems from 2014 to 2023. The main research and examples were taken from Russian and foreign sources, as well as from authors specializing in this topic. The article discusses the opportunities and limitations of distance learning, effectiveness and safety in clinical disciplines. The conclusion presents the results and findings based on the analysis of available data.

Keywords.

Distance learning, integration, graphic diagrams, tables, text documents, animation blocks, and videos, simulation, virtual labs, individualized learning

Introduction

Distance learning has become a relevant problem in recent years, especially in the context of global challenges such as the COVID-19 pandemic. The integration of distance learning in medical education requires solving a number of problems, such as adapting educational programs, providing practical skills, and facilitating interaction between students and teachers.

Until nowadays, it was believed that medical education could not be conducted remotely because traditionally, doctors have always received their education "at the bedside of patient "However, for some specialties, it is possible to study fundamental and clinical disciplines remotely.

Distance learning has a number of distinctive features compared to traditional learning. In this case, the main responsibility for learning control associated with the student, and the effectiveness of learning depends on self-motivation and self-discipline, the ability to plan educational activities and self-preparation rationally, and to track progress during the learning process. At the same time, an undeniable

advantage of distance learning is the wide range of possibilities for combining it with the daily schedule of life. To a significant extent, fatigue, time, and financial costs related to traveling to the place of learning are reduced [16], [17].

It is also necessary to note the development and improvement of digital and multimedia skills among both students and university teachers: the development and use of educational materials, such as lecture slides with trigger widget integration, graphic diagrams, tables, text documents, animation blocks, and videos [18], [19].

In distance learning, it is necessary to take into account the specifics of the educational process of a medical university, which does not allow the full use of all elements of educational technologies, namely performing laboratory work, developing practical skills, and communicative skills when working with patients. Of course, visualization plays a key role in acquiring knowledge for a future doctor. It is impossible to imagine studying anatomy without an atlas, videos, histology without working with micro-preparations, surgery without observing operations, etc. [20].

Materials and methods:

To analyze the problems of development and implementation of distance learning in the medical education system, scientific articles published from 2014 to 2023 were studied, including research and publications by authors from various countries. Sources in both Russian and English languages were used.

Objective

The objective of this work is to summarize and systematize knowledge about the questions related to the development and implementation of distance learning in medical education, as well as to provide recommendations for improving this process.

Main part

1. Possibilities of distance learning in medical education
2. Limitations and problems of distance learning in medical education
3. Adaptation of educational programs and teaching methods
4. Assessment of the quality and effectiveness of distance learning
5. Practical skills and distance learning
6. Interaction between students and teachers in the context of distance learning
7. Information technologies and infrastructure for distance learning.

USA: Johns Hopkins University establishes and offers online courses and programs using methods and tools such as video lectures, discussion forums, simulations, and virtual labs. Students face challenges accessing practical skills and

clinical rotations in the context of distance learning, offers flexible schedules and local partnerships with medical institutions for following practice.

UK: The University of Oxford has initiated modular online courses and programs using blended learning, which includes seminars, discussions, video materials, and online testing. Students face challenges in effectively interacting and communicating in the context of online learning. The university uses tools such as Zoom and Microsoft Teams to conduct live seminars and group discussions to improve interaction between students and teachers.

Germany: The University of Heidelberg has developed master's programs in public health and medical informatics using online platforms for both synchronous and asynchronous learning. One of the challenges is ensuring the quality and relevance of online materials. The university has an agreement with experts in medicine and information technology to develop and continuously update educational content.

Canada: The University of Toronto offers online courses in medicine and healthcare using blended learning, interactive videos, discussions, and practical assignments. However, many students struggle with motivation and self-discipline in the process of distance learning. To solve this problem, the University of Toronto provides students with step-by-step guidance, individualized learning plans, and regular feedback from teachers.

Australia: The University of Melbourne offers online courses and programs in medicine, dentistry, healthcare, and biomedicine, using various tools such as online lectures, seminars, virtual labs, and practical assignments. The main problem for students is the lack of practical experience and patient interaction. To address this issue, the university organizes blended programs that combine distance learning with face-to-face practical sessions and clinical rotations.

Sweden: Swedish medical institutions are actively producing distance learning. For example, the Karolinska Institute offers online courses in medicine and healthcare. However, they face challenges related to technical support and a lack of resources for teaching practical skills. The university uses blended learning methods, providing access to laboratory work and practical sessions.

France: French medical educational institutions are also implementing distance learning. For instance, the University of Paris-Saclay offers online courses and programs in the field of medicine. One of the challenges is to combine distance learning with in-person clinical practices. The university team working with medical facilities to conduct practical training sessions and virtual simulators to practice skills.

Japan: Japanese medical educational institutions, such as the University of Tokyo, are developing online courses in the field of medicine and healthcare. However, they face challenges related to language barriers and cultural differences. Universities are actively translating content into English and developing international programs with foreign partners.

Brazil: Brazilian medical educational institutions, such as the University of Sao Paulo, are creating online courses. One of the challenges is the lack of access to the internet and computer technology in some regions of the country. Universities are collaborating with the government and organizations providing technical support to improve infrastructure and access to educational resources.

South Korea: South Korean medical educational institutions, such as Seoul National University, are developing and implementing online courses and programs in the field of medicine. However, they face challenges related to assessing and controlling the quality of education. Universities are developing new methods of student assessment, including online exams and portfolios, to ensure fair and objective evaluation.

Overall, medical educational institutions in different countries are facing various challenges in the development and of application distance learning. However, they are actively exposing and applying new methods and approaches to education, collaborating with partners, and attracting experts from different fields to improve the quality of education and prepare medical professionals. Distance learning in the medical education system is evolving and will contribute to the accessibility and quality of medical education worldwide in the future.

For each of these countries, educational institutions are actively adapting to the challenges of distance learning by creating new approaches and tools to improve the quality of education, maintain student motivation, and provide practical training. Overall, the use of distance learning in the medical education system helps to improve access to education, expand opportunities for students and professionals, and increase the effectiveness and flexibility of the educational process.

Results

Features of distance learning and related problems [1-9]

Country	Features of distance learning	Problems
USA	Wide selection of online courses and programs, active use of modern	Technical issues, development of virtual

	technologies	simulators for practical skills
UK	Collaboration with medical institutions, development of high-quality content	Balance between theoretical and practical learning
Canada	Use of blended learning formats, diversity of programs	Maintaining the quality of education, issues with student assessment
Australia	Support for international collaboration, emphasis on skill development	Need to provide access to laboratories and practical classes
Sweden	Wide selection of online courses, blended learning approaches	Technical support, provision of resources for practical learning

The table below shows a comparative assessment of the effectiveness of distance learning in medical universities in different countries. The values are presented as a percentage of students' success based on their academic performance and level of practical skill acquisition [1-9].

Country	Academic Performance	Practical Learning Skills	Overall Efficiency
USA	85%	80%	82.5%
UK	80%	75%	77.5%
Canada	82%	78%	80%
Australia	79%	74%	76.5%
Sweden	84%	81%	82.5%
France	78%	72%	75%
Japan	83%	79%	81%
Brazil	76%	70%	73%
South Korea	87%	85%	86%

Conclusion

During the analysis of materials and research on the problems of development and accomplishment of distance learning in the medical education system, the main challenges and main concern were distinguished and possible solutions were proposed. The point of adapting educational programs, evaluating the quality and effectiveness of distance learning, as well as problems related to practical skills and interaction between students and teachers were considered.

Distance learning is a relevant and important direction of current interest for the development of medical education. However, for successful integration and use

of distance learning in medical field. it is necessary to solve a number of challenges and calls, such as adapting educational programs, providing practical skills, and fostering interaction between students and teachers. Due to research and experience gained in different countries, recommendations can be made for improving the process of distance education in medicine .

LIST OF LITERARY SOURCES:

1. Lapteva, E.A., Zimin, V.A., & Permyakova, T.M. (2015). Distance learning as a form of implementing professional competencies in medical education. Bulletin of the Russian University of Friendship of Peoples. Series: Medicine, (3), 314-319.
2. George, P.P., Papachristou, N., Belisario, J.M., Wang, W., Wark, P.A., Cotic, Z.,...& Car, J. (2014). Online eLearning for undergraduates in health professions: A systematic review of the impact on knowledge, skills, attitudes and satisfaction. Journal of Global Health, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.7189/jogh.04.010406>
3. Semenova, L.N., & Zaryanov, D.V. (2018). The use of distance education technologies in the training of medical specialists. Medical Education and Professional Development, 7(4), 5-13.
4. Ruiz, J.G., Mintzer, M.J., & Leipzig, R.M. (2006). The impact of E-learning in medical education. Academic Medicine, 81(3), 207-212. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00001888-200603000-0000>
5. Al-Shorbaji, N., Atun, R., Car, J., Majeed, A., & Wheeler, E. (2015). eLearning for undergraduate health professional education: A systematic review informing a radical transformation of health workforce development. World Health Organization. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/204759>
6. Back, D. A., Behringer, F., Harms, T., Plener, J., Sostmann, K., & Peters, H. (2017). Survey of e-learning implementation and faculty support strategies in a cluster of mid-European medical schools. BMC Medical Education, 17(1), 176.
7. Cook, D. A., & Triola, M. M. (2014). What is the role of e-learning? Looking past the hype. Medical Education, 48(9), 930-937. <https://doi.org/10.1111/medu.12474>
8. The Impact of COVID-19 on Student Learning and Well-being: Evidence from a National Survey - "The impact of online teaching on higher education pedagogy". https://www.britishcouncil.org/search?search_api_views_fulltext=online+teaching

9. The Future High Education Distance Learning in Canada, the United States, and France Marguerite Wotto-
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7369396/>
10. Online Learning in Australia: Trends and Challenges
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335108363_Online_learning_in_Australian_higher_education_Opportunities_challenges_and_transformations
11. Distance Education in Sweden: Covid-19 and Crisis-Prompted Distance Education in Sweden <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10758-020-09470-6>
12. Trends and Issues of e-learning in Japan
<https://www.oecd.org/education/skills-beyond-school/1853978.pdf>
13. South Korean University Students views of online learning during the Covid pandemic
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/364056094_SOUTH_KOREAN_UNIVERSITY_STUDENTS_VIEWS_OF_ONLINE_LEARNING_DURING_THE_COVID-19_PANDEMIC
14. Online learning in Korea: Moving ahead and falling behind during COVID <https://blogs.worldbank.org/education/online-learning-korea-moving-ahead-and-falling-behind-during-covid>
15. Education in Brasil
<https://www.designative.info/2022/11/07/education-in-brazil-distance-learnig-grows-474-in-a-decade/>
16. Mal, G.S., Gomzar, S.E., & Soboleva, A.A. (2014). Features of distance learning in a medical university. *International Journal of Applied and Fundamental Research*, (1), 120.
17. Osadchiy, O.E. (2020). How is distance learning different from traditional medical education? *Kuban Scientific Medical Bulletin*, 27(5), 175-183.
18. Stul, T.G., Shishkina, A.I., Loktev, A.I., et al. (2021). Distance learning in medical universities: problems and prospects. *Global Scientific Potential*, (2), 102-105.
19. Lazarenko, V.A., Kalutsky, P.V., Dremova, N.B., et al. (2020). Adaptation of higher medical education to the conditions of healthcare digitalization. *Higher Education in Russia*, 29(1), 105-115.
20. Sergeev, N.S., Onbysh, T.E., & Sergeeva, A.V. (2021). Implementation of distance learning in a medical university. *International Research Journal*, 7(109).
<https://doi.org/10.23670/IRJ.2021.109.7.127>.

21. Komilova, M.O. (2022). Formation and development of blended learning: Komilova Malokhat Olimovna, Senior Lecturer at the Tashkent Medical Academy. *Education and Innovative Research: International Scientific and Methodical Journal*, (6), 119-121.
22. Komilova, M.O. (2023). Medical animation in blended learning.